

University of Nebraska - Lincoln

DigitalCommons@University of Nebraska - Lincoln

Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

Libraries at University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Summer 6-21-2020

Factors influencing Higher Similarity and Plagiarism amongst Research Scholars: a Comparative Case Study of two Indian Universities- Centers of Higher Education

Deepti Madaan
libn_davc@yahoo.co.in

Rupak Chakravarty, Prof. DLIS
Panjab University, Chandigarh, India, RUPAK@PUCHD.AC.IN

Follow this and additional works at: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac>

Part of the [Library and Information Science Commons](#)

Madaan, Deepti and Chakravarty,, Rupak Prof. DLIS, "Factors influencing Higher Similarity and Plagiarism amongst Research Scholars: a Comparative Case Study of two Indian Universities- Centers of Higher Education" (2020). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 4287.
<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4287>

Factors influencing Higher Similarity and Plagiarism amongst Research Scholars: a Comparative Case Study of two Indian Universities

Deepti Madaan* Prof. Rupak Chakravarty**

*Research Scholar, DLIS, PU, Chandigarh and Librarian, DAVC-10, Chandigarh

**Prof. Rupak Chakravarty, DLIS, Panjab University, Chandigarh

Abstract

Higher Education is gaining momentum in every domain. There is a strong passion and pressure to undertake research and find solutions to the problems plaguing Higher Education. In the pressure to enhance one's career prospects leads to instances of academic misconduct like plagiarism which is adversely affecting the academia. Different studies have brought into light different reasons behind it. This study is also an attempt to analyse the reasons/factors which create hindrance in the way of original research. The study explores various factors which are prevalent among the research scholars of social sciences and sciences of GNDU, Amritsar and PU, Chandigarh. The findings of this study will unfold new vistas for the faculty, library professionals and the institutions to work collectively for guiding the researchers in overcoming those hurdles. It is hoped that by countering these factors or removing these obstacles the originality in research can be brought in, duplicacy of work would be avoided and research would become more focussed and valid.

Introduction:

Swift development in Information and communication technologies has led to an alarming increase in the instances of academic misconduct with plagiarism emerging as the serious one Chen and Chou (2016). In every domain of academics from language, literature, humanities to sciences, plagiarism has been adversely affecting the quality of study and research Debnath (2016). There is lack of awareness among students and researchers for giving due credit for borrowed ideas, texts and images etc Helgesson (2014). Consequently there is a dire need to bring and promote academic literacy for proper attribution in academic writing and research Mah and Ting (2013). At the same time the perceptions, practices, attitudes and the reasons for plagiarism has emerged as another area of study Harji et al. (2017). Academic/social/family/peer pressure, language barrier, lack of competence, tech enabled easy access to sources of information, lack of proper citation skills are some compelling factors giving rise to duplicacy in research. This paper focuses on the reasons which become hurdles for the research scholars of sciences and social sciences of the two leading Higher Educational Institutions of the Nation viz GNDU, Amritsar and PU, Chandigarh.

Statement of the Problem:

In the ongoing academic scenario, research in every faculty is being done vigorously. Digital revolution has promoted the dissemination of information to a great extent. Side by side instances of academic dishonesty in study and research have also increased manifold. An offshoot of this menace is plagiarism which is adversely affecting the quality of research. There are a number of factors which play pivotal role in changing the approach towards academic writings and research. This paper is an attempt

towards bringing those factors to light with special emphasis on the research scholars of two Universities i.e., Panjab University, Chandigarh and Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar. This study will enable the authors to get an idea about the factors which ultimately become hurdles in ethical writing and research. This study is important in bringing confidence, morality and originality amongst the research scholars by avoiding those compelling reasons or factors. These identified factors have also widened the role of faculty members and library professionals in enhancing the perception and attitude of research scholars.

Research Questions:

What are the various factors which lead to plagiarism amongst the research scholars of GNDU and PU?

Or is there any significant difference between the prevalence of reasons amongst the research scholars of GNDU and PU?

What are the various factors behind plagiarism amongst the research scholars of Social Sciences and Sciences of GNDU and PU?

Or is there any significant difference between the prevalence of reasons amongst the research scholars of Social Sciences and Sciences of GNDU and PU?

Scope:

This study has taken into account the research scholars of two universities viz Panjab University (PU), Chandigarh and Guru Nanak Dev University (GNDU), Amritsar. Sample of 50 research scholars each from both the Universities have been taken. Five disciplines of Sciences comprising Botany, Zoology, Maths, Physics and Chemistry and five disciplines of Social Sciences comprising Sociology, Political Science, History, Economics and Psychology are the domains of the study.

Methodology:

Questionnaire comprising questions on 5 point likert scale was formulated and circulated amongst the research scholars of two Universities. Data collected was processed and analysed using SPSS Descriptive Statistics i.e., mean, standard deviation and chi square.

Research implications:

This paper may improve the quality of research, making it academically ethical and practically need based. The researchers will realise the value of originality and morality and will incorporate it in their academic pursuits. The role of faculty, higher educational institutions and library professionals will be widened as they will be implementing the regulations of Academic Integrity formulated by UGC. Software would be deployed to check the originality in research work.

Social implications:

The research paper at hand may facilitate discussion, debate and solutions to the problems underlying in the topic. The researchers will feel motivated to bring ingenuity in their work. They will come up with innovative ideas bringing freshness in academics.

Originality/Value:

Before writing this paper, an extensive study was undertaken to know ills affecting the research in Higher Education. So far no such comparative case study focusing on the research scholars of sciences and social sciences belonging to two institutions of higher learning has been undertaken.

Review of literature:

Plagiarism has become all pervasive problem affecting not only academics but also art, music, movies etc. During the course of our study and reviewing other previous work, number of factors have come to the fore which compel the students and researchers to plagiarise.

“Lack of awareness” Smith et al. (2007), has been a major factor in instances of academic misconduct. “The students don’t have the understanding of rules of attribution” (Armstrong and Delbridge (2008), “the students do not know what is allowed and what is not” is another factor responsible for unethical writing as quoted by (Razera et al. (2010). Lack of awareness in realising that writing word by word is incorrect even if the reference is given and lack of basic awareness about plagiarism (Debnath (2016) Lack of awareness on severity of plagiarism and its consequences and policies adopted by the Universities as explained by Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013) in their work.

“Personal reasons” as the broad factor mentioned in the study undertaken by Smith et al. (2007) also lead to a academic misconduct. “Weak writing and reading comprehension” has been quoted by Harji et al. (2017); Lofstrom and Kupila (2017). Difficult assignments which become complex to complete become reason for plagiarism, Harji et al. (2017); Armstrong and Delbridge (2008) Lack of interest in learning by the students is another factor behind plagiarism as quoted by (Harji et al. (2017). “I copy even if assignment is easy” (Harji et al. (2017).; carelessness (Lofstrom and Kupila (2017); slack attitudes amongst Students (Lei and Hu (2015) are some of the reasons which lead to unethical writings. Lack of confidence in writing skills (Debnath (2016). Taking plagiarism as not wrong (Harji et al. (2017); Razera et al. (2010) ;Lofstrom and Kupila (2017); Chen and Chou (2016) , confidence of never getting caught (Harji et al. (2017); Lofstrom and Kupila (2017); Armstrong and Delbridge (2008); Debnath (2016), low risk involvement in plagiarism (Lei and Hu (2015) are other factors which lead to Plagiarism as described by the authors mentioned alongwith. “Students feel proud whose assignments are copied more and students believe that copying others works is a way to show respect to them” has been quoted by Chen and Chou, 2016. “Lack of interest to work hard” Jereb (2018), Less research experience and lack of interest, lack of understanding of subject, Chaturvedi (2018) are the factors explained by various authors which create hurdles in ethical writings.

“Availability of internet has eased the way of accessing information” (Smith et al., 2007; Debnath (2016). Easy to copy and paste has been mentioned in the study conducted by Harji et al. (2017). “Easy access to material on Internet” quoted by Armstrong and Delbridge (2008), “Students see plagiarism as easy way

with the spread of computer and internet" (Razera et al. (2010) Lots of material on Internet as mentioned in the work of Babalola (2012). "Easiness of plagiarising" discussed by Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013). Jereb (2018) has quoted "ICT and Web" in his work in which various factors ranging from easily available research material on Internet to easy copying and pasting to unawareness of citing the reference sources has been mentioned. "Easy access to search engines like Google" given by Guraya and Guraya (2018). Such factors promote convenient copying and pasting, thus leading to plagiarism.

"Lack of Competence" quoted by (Smith et al. (2007) "Research ability is limited" (Chen and Chou (2016), "Not able to handle the workload" (Harji et al. (2017); "lack of time" (Hosny and Fatima (2014) "Cannot express in my own words" Harji et al. (2017. Lazy/bad time management (Armstrong and Delbridge (2008), Razera et al. (2010), "Underestimate his/her own abilities" (Razera et al. (2010) are some of the reasons as revealed in various studies which need to be considered to curb this academic menace. Academic skills as the collective term given by Jereb (2018) to the cluster of reasons like poor time management, unable to find research material, weak writing and reading comprehension skills and inability to express ones own ideas. "Teaching factors" as quoted by Jereb (2018) includes sub factors like "too many assignment in less time, not satisfied with the course content, poor explanation and plagiarism is not explained". "Lack of time, casual approach, complexity of topics make students and researchers plagiarize", Guraya and Guraya (2018). "Lesser time due to other engagements", "lack of creativity in thinking", have been discussed by Chaturvedi (2018).

"Pressure" as the main heading was used by Smith et al. (2007); Lei and Hu (2015). "Pressure to submit assignment on time" Chen and Chou (2016), "external pressure to succeed" Harji et al. (2017); "pressure to complete overloaded assignment in less time" quoted by Babalola (2012); Lofstrom and Kupila (2017), "lack of time to meet the deadline", Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013). "Intense pressure for publication in academia for career progression" Debnath, 2016; Chaturvedi, 2018. "Family/work pressure" (Lofstrom and Kupila (2017), "to get good grades" Armstrong and Delbridge (2008); Hosny and Fatima (2014), Razera et al. (2010), Babalola (2012); Jereb (2018). "To pass the course at any price" (Razera et al. (2010) Jereb (2018) has gathered the students' responses to number of pressures like family, peer, stress, faculty, money, fear of failure and job pressure. Pressure from various fronts like peer, parental, social make one resort to copy paste as given by Guraya and Guraya (2018). "Competition at workplace", Chaturvedi (2018). Unable to cope with these pressures, students and researchers take to plagiarism.

Peer influences (Harji et al. (2017); Lofstrom and Kupila (2017); Armstrong and Delbridge (2008)) amongst the student community is the common factor behind plagiarism.

Citations as the broader heading quoted by Harji et al. (2017); Not knowing the proper way of citations Chen and Chou (2016); Babalola (2012); Lofstrom and Kupila (2017). Use one's own ideas or text from their own previously published works without citations is not plagiarism (Debnath (2016)

Students feel that their instances of plagiarism will remain unnoticed by the faculty. (Harji et al. (2017); Chen and Chou (2016) ;Babalola (2012) ; Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013)

"Institution' the broader term was quoted by Smith (2007) which included unawareness on legal implications of plagiarism. Jereb (2018) has highlighted such factors under the heading "Regulation".

This includes factors from faculty regulation to university regulation to the consequences and penalties. “Lack of trainings on plagiarism at the institutional level, those who plagiarise and those who don’t plagiarise are given the same treatment, there is no difference in evaluation of the plagiarised and non-plagiarised texts”, Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013), “lack of institutional regulatory policy”, Guraya and Guraya (2018). “Lack of formal orientation on plagiarism”, Chaturvedi (2018)

Miscellaneous factors: “Students lack motivation” (Razera et al. (2010); “students don’t know how to search for library material” Babalola (2012), “Students lack interest in topic” Razera et al. (2010); Chen and Chou (2016). “Language barrier” Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013), “Since everyone else is doing it” Rezanejad and Rezaei (2013). “Pride” major factor quoted by Jereb (2018) included “not getting embarrassed in front of family, teachers and peers, fear of poor performance compel the students to plagiarise” and so on. “Easier to plagiarise than to work” Jereb (2018) False perception that “information on net is in public domain and can be used in any way”, Guraya and Guraya (2018). “Poor academic culture”, “Lack of guidance by superior” and “lack of academic resource support at library to refer to new topics”, Chaturvedi (2018). Such never ending terms/phrases identified as factors by various authors in various studies.

Role of UGC in promoting Academic Integrity:

For the past many decades UGC has been actively engaged in promoting Higher Education as well as bringing high standards of ethics in study and research. In pursuance of this, UGC has formulated.....

Research Survey Instrument:

Keeping in view the various factors which have been explored and discussed in above mentioned studies, the authors of this study have formed a research survey instrument which consisted following questions and the responses were measured on a 5 Point Likert Scale.

Reasons
Similarity in the topics of research and excessive information available on them thus making the research work easier
Deliberate ignorance about the plagiarism
Lack of urge/desire to make efforts in undertaking research
English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers
Lack of interest in some topics of research
Academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the research work
Limited time coupled with lack of time management skills on the part of researchers
Time and effort getting saved in copying the information from Internet
No extra credit given for citations
Great time and effort involved in quoting the citation in a standard format
Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author
Excessive information available on the same topic making it difficult for the author to cite its proper source
Not feeling the need to cite one’s own previously published work thus leading to plagiarism
Owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought

It is a complex task to quote web based sources
I find it very time and effort consuming for writing the references
I've never been trained regarding the proper way of attribution

Data Analysis:

Figure 1

The bar chart depicts the demographic details of the respondents of both the Universities in different age groups. The authors have taken into account the research scholars of 4 Age Groups. The research scholars fall under the category of below 25 in GNDU and PU are 6% and 5% respectively. In the age group of 25-30 there are 38% research scholars from GNDU and 36% from PU. The research scholars of the age group 30-35 are 4% GNDU and 7% from PU. Rest of the respondents in both the Universities are from Above 35 age group.

Figure 2

Continuing with the demographic details of the respondents, the female research scholars constitute 32% in GNDU as compared to 33% female research scholars in PU. 18% of the respondents from GNDU are males and 17% from PU are males.

Figure 3

The research scholars under this study come from the period 2014 to 2019 as per their year of registration. The maximum no. of registered research scholars of GNDU under study are from the year 2017 and 2018 i.e., 13. 10 research scholars belong to the year of registration 2016 in GNDU. 8 Research scholars under this study from GNDU are from the year 2019 and 6 from the year 2015 in GNDU.

In Panjab University there are 18 research scholars in the year 2017 are part of this study. 12 research scholars are from 2016, 10 from 2015, 6 from the year 2018 and 3 from 2019 and one respondent from the year 2014.

Figure 4

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.34	1.171	2.82	1.380

15% of the research scholars from GNDU agree and 9% strongly agree that Similarity in the topics of research and excessive information available on them make the research work easier is the reason behind plagiarism whereas 17% of the research scholars from Panjab University disagree and 9% strongly disagree to it.

Figure 5

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.26	1.139	2.60	1.245

23% of the research scholars from GNDU agree and 4% strongly agree that deliberate ignorance about the plagiarism make them resort to while 14% research scholars from PU agree and 2% strongly agree about the same.

Figure 6

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.26	1.065	3.30	1.359

Lack of urge/desire to make efforts in undertaking research make 22% of the research scholars from GNDU in favour of this statement. 13% of the scholars from PU agree and 12 % strongly agree to this reason.

Figure 7

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.48	1.147	2.40	1.030

22% of the respondents from GNDU confirm to “English becoming a linguistic barrier for them” while 8% strongly agree to this statement. Whereas the figures of Panjab University shows 19% of the scholars disagree to this statement and 13% remained neutral for this reason.

Figure 8

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.20	1.069	3.28	1.196

Lack of interest in some topics of research make 25% of the scholars from GNDU agree to it while 13 % of the respondents from GNDU disagree with it. 15% of the research scholars from PU agree to it and 8% strongly agree to this reason while 15% remained neutral.

Figure 9

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.52	1.328	3.04	1.399

19% of the research scholars from GNDU agree and 13% strongly agree to the statement that academic/peer/family/social pressure make them pursue the research work whereas in PU 11% agree to this reason and 10% strongly agree to this statement. However 13% of the scholars from PU disagree and 8% strongly disagree to this reason.

Figure 10

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.74	1.046	3.66	1.136

The bar diagram of GNDU reveals that 22% of the respondents agree and 12% strongly agree to the above mentioned reason i.e., time constraints. 20% of the research scholars from PU also give due weightage to the same reason of time constraints. However 14% of the respondents from PU disagree and 8% strongly disagree to this reason.

Figure 11

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.52	1.035	2.96	1.340

Findings reveal that 29% of the research scholars from GNDU agree with the statement time and effort getting saved in copying the information from the Internet however 14% research scholars from PU agree with this and 14% disagree with this reason.

Figure 12

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.08	1.104	3.34	1.002

It has been found that the 22% research scholars from GNDU agree that no extra credit is given for citations. However 14% from the same University disagree with the same statement and 8% of the respondents from GNDU remained neutral. The bar shows that 17% agree with the statement and 16% remained neutral on the above mentioned reason.

Figure 13

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.26	1.259	3.44	1.110

23% of the research scholars GNDU agree and 6% strongly agree that lot of time and effort is involved in quoting the citations in a standard format. In contrast to this, 18% research scholars from PU agree and 9% strongly agree with this reason. However 10% research scholars were neutral on this statement.

Figure 14

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.54	0.862	3.68	0.819

36% of the respondents from GNDU confirm to the reason that lack of requisite knowledge comes in the way of quoting the original author. However in PU 21% of the research scholars agree and 8% strongly agree with this reason. 18% of the respondents from PU remained neutral.

Figure 15

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.24	0.960	3.48	1.015

The picture shows that 24% of the respondents from GNDU and PU agree that the excessive information on the same topic makes it difficult for the author to cite its proper source. 14% of the respondents from GNDU remained neutral as compared to 9% of the respondents from PU who were neutral on this reason. 10% of the research scholars from PU disagree with this.

Figure 16

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
2.90	1.111	3.16	1.201

The respondents from GNDU who do not feel the need to cite one's own previously published work are 17%. However 16% do not agree with this and 10% remained neutral. In contrast to this, 14% agree, 14% neutral and 7% strongly agree with this reason.

Figure 17

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.56	0.787	3.66	0.961

34% of the research scholars from GNDU agree that owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought. While 20% from PU respondents agree with this reason. 13% of the respondents from PU disagree and 7% strongly disagree with this reason.

Figure 18

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.50	0.886	3.40	0.904

The data shows that 34% of the respondents from GNDU agree that it is a complex task to quote web based sources while 9% disagree and 5% remained neutral. Data of PU reveals that 22% confirm to this statement and 14% remained neutral. 22% of the research scholars from PU disagree with this.

Figure 19

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.14	1.088	3.36	0.802

Writing the references is a time and effort consuming task as felt by the research scholars of both the universities. The data shows that 19% of the respondents from GNDU and 22% of the respondents from PU agree with this. However 15% and 18% of the respondents from GNDU and PU respectively remained neutral. 8% of the respondents from both the universities disagree with this reason.

Figure 20

GNDU ; N=50		PU ; N=50	
MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D
3.36	1.120	3.10	1.249

23% of the research scholars from GNDU agree and 6% strongly agree that they have not been trained as to how to attribute properly. As compared to this, data of PU shows that 13% of the research scholars also agree with this statement. 13% of the respondents from GNDU and 16% of the respondents from PU disagree with this statement.

Referring to above mentioned Figures 1-20, Mean values of the reasons of the research scholars of GNDU reveal that they highly supported "limited time coupled with time management skills" (Mean 3.74) followed

by “owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which source the information was sought” (Mean 3.56) Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author (Mean 3.54), Time and effort getting saved in copying the information from Internet (Mean 3.52), Academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the research work (Mean 3.52), It is a complex task to quote web based sources (Mean 3.50) and English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers (Mean 3.48) are the factors which have mostly been considered by the research scholars of GNDU, Amritsar. The mean figures of all the reasons as shown by the Panjab University bar diagrams depict that lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author takes the top position with the mean of 3.68 followed by owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought, taken the second position same as GNDU but with the greater mean value of 3.66. The other prominent reasons are Limited time coupled with lack of time management skills on the part of researchers (Mean 3.66), Excessive information available on the same topic making it difficult for the author to cite its proper source (Mean 3.48), Great time and effort involved in quoting the citation in a standard format (Mean 3.44) and It is a complex task to quote web based sources (Mean 3.40)

To find out the significant difference between the reasons prevalent amongst the research scholars of two Universities, the data was further analysed using Chi Square through SPSS (**Refer Table 1**) The results of the cross tabulation is shown in the below mentioned table. The figures reveal that there are 5 reasons which show significantly different readings. English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers is the highly significant factor with the p value of .0001. This has been followed by lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author with the p value coming to .001. Owing to plenty of resources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought was another major factor with the p value of .005. Lack of interest in some topics of research (p value .023), time and effort getting saved in copying the information from the Internet has emerged out as a reason whose p value shows significance difference with p value 0.032 and It's a complex task to quote web based sources (p value .046) are the other major factors.

Table 1

	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Similarity in the topics of research and excessive information available on them thus making the research work easier	8.453	4	.076
Deliberate ignorance about the plagiarism	7.597	4	0.108
Lack of urge/desire to make efforts in undertaking research	8.706	4	0.069
English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers	22.926	4	.0001**
Lack of interest in some topics of research	11.309	4	.023*
Academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the research work	5.278	4	.260
Limited time coupled with lack of time management skills on the part of researchers	1.651	4	0.8
Time and effort getting saved in copying the information from Internet	10.586	4	.032*
No extra credit given for citations	7.774	4	0.1
Great time and effort involved in quoting the citation in a standard format	6.630	4	0.157
Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author	18.794	4	.001**
Excessive information available on the same topic making it difficult for the author to cite its proper source	5.881	4	0.208
Not feeling the need to cite one's own previously published work thus leading to plagiarism	5.119	4	0.275
Owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought	12.860	3	.005**
It is a complex task to quote web based sources	9.687	4	.046*
I find it very time and effort consuming for writing the references	5.692	4	0.223
I have never been trained regarding the proper way of attribution	4.641	4	0.326

GNDU Social Sciences vs PU Social Sciences

Deep analysis was done through SPSS using Mann Whitney test for finding out the differences in reasons amongst the research scholars in two domains of Sciences and Social Sciences of GNDU and PU as shown in **Table 2**. The below mentioned table gives an idea of the reasons which the research scholars of social sciences from both the universities feel prominent. English becoming the linguistic barrier is the highly significant factor with the p value of 0.000. The research scholars of social sciences feel that academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the research work is one of the major compelling factors with p value of 0.005. Similarity in the topics of research and excessive information available on them thus making the research work easier shows another significant difference with p value of 0.027.

Table 2

FACTORS	GNDU - SOCIAL SCIENCES			PU - SOCIAL SCIENCES			Mann-	p
	N	Mean Rank	Sum of	N	Mean	Sum of Ranks		
Similarity in the topics of research and excessive	25	29.92	748.00	25	21.08	527.00	2.211	0.027
Deliberate ignorance about the plagiarism	25	29.18	729.50	25	21.82	545.50	1.865	0.062
Lack of urge/desire to make efforts in undertaking	25	25.44	636.00	25	25.56	639.00	0.030	0.976
English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers	25	34.88	872.00	25	16.12	403.00	4.703	0.000
Lack of interest in some topics of research	25	26.60	665.00	25	24.40	610.00	0.560	0.575
Academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the	25	31.08	777.00	25	19.92	498.00	2.821	0.005
Limited time coupled with lack of time management skills	25	24.82	620.50	25	26.18	654.50	0.348	0.728
Time and effort getting saved in copying the information	25	26.30	657.50	25	24.70	617.50	0.410	0.682
No extra credit given for citations	25	24.70	617.50	25	26.30	657.50	0.407	0.684
Great time and effort involved in quoting the citation in a	25	22.76	569.00	25	28.24	706.00	1.448	0.148
Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the	25	24.78	619.50	25	26.22	655.50	0.424	0.672
Excessive information available on the same topic making	25	23.54	588.50	25	27.46	686.50	1.044	0.297
Not feeling the need to cite one's own previously	25	22.26	556.50	25	28.74	718.50	1.620	0.105
Owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which	25	23.12	578.00	25	27.88	697.00	1.293	0.196
It is a complex task to quote web based sources	25	25.86	646.50	25	25.14	628.50	0.204	0.838
I find it very time and effort consuming for writing the	25	21.82	545.50	25	29.18	729.50	1.875	0.061
I have never been trained regarding the proper way of	25	24.14	603.50	25	26.86	671.50	0.687	0.492

GNDU Sciences vs PU Sciences

To get a clear understanding of the reasons which are prevalent amongst the research scholars of sciences from GNDU and PU (Table 3), a thorough analysis of the data was done using the same Mann Whitney Test of SPSS. The table reveals that time and effort getting saved in copying the information from internet has the p value of 0.011. I have never been trained regarding the proper way of attribution is the another major reason which reflects the p value of 0.029.

Table 3

FACTORS	GNDU SCIENCE			PU SCIENCE				
	N	Mean	Sum of	N	Mean	Sum of	Mann-	p
Similarity in the topics of research and excessive	25	26.94	673.50	25	24.06	601.50	0.714	0.475
Deliberate ignorance about the plagiarism	25	29.16	729.00	25	21.84	546.00	1.837	0.066
Lack of urge/desire to make efforts in undertaking	25	24.70	617.50	25	26.30	657.50	0.401	0.688
English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers	25	29.30	732.50	25	21.70	542.50	1.898	0.058
Lack of interest in some topics of research	25	23.58	589.50	25	27.42	685.50	0.970	0.332
Academic/peer/family/social pressure to complete the	25	25.16	629.00	25	25.84	646.00	0.169	0.866
Limited time coupled with lack of time management skills	25	26.74	668.50	25	24.26	606.50	0.634	0.526
Time and effort getting saved in copying the information	25	30.50	762.50	25	20.50	512.50	2.547	0.011
No extra credit given for citations	25	23.28	582.00	25	27.72	693.00	1.132	0.258
Great time and effort involved in quoting the citation in a	25	26.70	667.50	25	24.30	607.50	0.604	0.546
Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the	25	25.36	634.00	25	25.64	641.00	0.073	0.941
Excessive information available on the same topic making	25	23.98	599.50	25	27.02	675.50	0.780	0.436
Not feeling the need to cite one's own previously	25	25.64	641.00	25	25.36	634.00	0.070	0.944
Owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which	25	26.40	660.00	25	24.60	615.00	0.473	0.636
It is a complex task to quote web based sources	25	27.00	675.00	25	24.00	600.00	0.784	0.433
I find it very time and effort consuming for writing the	25	27.12	678.00	25	23.88	597.00	0.841	0.400
I have never been trained regarding the proper way of	25	29.80	745.00	25	21.20	530.00	2.178	0.029

Conclusion:

Plagiarism is an act of academic dishonesty which puts question mark on the integrity, fairness, accountability etc. of students and researchers ultimately deteriorating the quality of research in their respective HEIs. Preventive measures should be taken actively to curb it. It curbs originality and rise of innovative research. Preventing it requires collective efforts of all the stakeholders who have to work with open mind with UGC becoming the first and foremost formulating "Promotion of Academic Integrity and Prevention of Plagiarism in Higher Educational Institutions in 2018. Consequently, all HEIs are following these regulations. There is a dire need to spread awareness regarding ethics in academics and research amongst the research scholars and the students. No excuse can save the wrong doer even if it is intentional or unintentional or even self plagiarism. Sometimes, one's own work is cited without proper attribution. Doing away with this requires holistic approach. As the results revealed that the most prevalent factors leading to plagiarism are "English becoming a linguistic barrier for some researchers", "Time and effort getting saved in copying the information from Internet", "Lack of requisite knowledge in the way of quoting the original author", "Owing to plenty of sources referred, I forgot from which particular source the information was sought", "It is a complex task to quote web based sources". Starting from the graduation or post graduation level, the students should be apprised about this wrong doing, it's adverse consequences. Training programs should be conducted at the institutional level to make the researchers learn about what all plagiarism is, its types, forms and the most important is to make them aware about the right way of attribution of both the print and web based sources. They should also be counselled about the ways of doing proper time management and how to cope up with different kinds of pressures.

References

Armstrong, L., & Delbridge, R. (2008). Final year undergraduate student plagiarism: academic staff and student perceptions.

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7a6a/1ffae289e01a5ce130e1b89c5fdd06d93836.pdf>

Babolola, Y. T. (2012). Awareness and incidence of plagiarism among undergraduates in a Nigerian private university. *African Journal of Library, Archives & Information Science*, 22(1), 53-60.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/290023589_Awareness_and_Incidence_of_Plagiarism_among_Undergraduates_in_a_Nigerian_Private_University

- Chaturvedi, V. (2018). Analysing the factors leading to plagiarism amongst researchers: An exploratory approach. *International Journal of Management Studies*, *V*(3(7)), 87.
[https://doi.org/10.18843/ijms/v5i3\(7\)/10](https://doi.org/10.18843/ijms/v5i3(7)/10)
- Chen, Y., & Chou, C. (2015). Are we on the same page? College students' and faculty's perception of student plagiarism in Taiwan. *Ethics & Behavior*, *27*(1), 53-73.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2015.1123630>
- Debnath, J. (2016). Plagiarism: A silent epidemic in scientific writing – Reasons, recognition and remedies. *Medical Journal Armed Forces India*, *72*(2), 164-167.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mjafi.2016.03.010>
- Guraya, S. Y., & Guraya, S. S. (2017). The confounding factors leading to plagiarism in academic writing and some suggested remedies: a systematic review. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association*, *67*(5), 767-772. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28507368>
- Harji, M. B., Ismail, Z., Chetty, T. N., & Letchumanan, K. (2017). Technical and non-technical programme students' attitudes and reasons for plagiarism. *English Language Teaching*, *10*(11), 141. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v10n11p141>
- Helgesson, G. (2014). Time for a change in the understanding of what constitutes text plagiarism? *Research Ethics*, *10*(4), 187-195. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016114552686>
- Hosny, M., & Fatima, S. (2014). Attitude of students towards cheating and plagiarism: University case study. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, *14*(8), 748-757.
<https://doi.org/10.3923/jas.2014.748.757>
- Jereb, E., Perc, M., Lämmlein, B., Jerebic, J., Urh, M., Podbregar, I., & Šprajc, P. (2018). undefined. *PLOS ONE*, *13*(8), e0202252. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0202252>

Lei, J., & Hu, G. (2014). Chinese university EFL teachers' perceptions of plagiarism. *Higher Education, 70*(3), 551-565. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-014-9855-5>

Löfström, E., & Kupila, P. (2013). The instructional challenges of student plagiarism. *Journal of Academic Ethics, 11*(3), 231-242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-013-9181-z>

Löfström, E., & Kupila, P. (2013). The instructional challenges of student plagiarism. *Journal of Academic Ethics, 11*(3), 231-242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-013-9181-z>

Mah, F. S., & Ting, S. H. (2013, June). *Academic literacy: Plagiarism in the Pre-University Students' academic writing* [Paper presentation]. International Conference on Learning and Teaching, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259939925_Mah_F_Ting_S_H_2013_June_28-29_Academic_literacy_Plagiarism_in_preuniversity_students'_academic_writing_Paper_presented_at_International_Conference_on_Learning_and_Teaching_2013_Shah_Alam_Selangor_Ma

Razera, D., Verhagen, H., Pargman, T. C., & Ramberg, R. (2010). *Plagiarism awareness, perception and attitudes among students and teachers in Swedish higher education* [Paper presentation]. 4th International plagiarism conference- towards an authentic future, UK.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242738794_Plagiarism_awareness_perception_and_attitudes_among_students_and_teachers_in_Swedish_higher_education_-_a_case_study

Rezanejad, A., & Rezaei, S. (2013). Academic dishonesty at universities: The case of plagiarism among Iranian language students. *Journal of Academic Ethics, 11*(4), 275-295.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-013-9193-8>

Smith, M., Ghazali, N., & Fatimah Noor Minhad, S. (2007). Attitudes towards plagiarism among undergraduate accounting students: Malaysian evidence. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 15(2), 122-146. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13217340710823350>

Teodorescu, D., & Andrei, T. (2008). Faculty and peer influences on academic integrity: College cheating in Romania. *Higher Education*, 57(3), 267-282. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-008-9143-3>

Teodorescu, D., & Andrei, T. (2008). Faculty and peer influences on academic integrity: College cheating in Romania. *Higher Education*, 57(3), 267-282. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-008-9143-3>